

Influence of Structural Transition on Dielectric and PE measurements of La doped Bismuth Titanate Polycrystals

M. G. Shankar,^{1,2,*} R. Thiyagarajan,¹ P. Jagadeesan,^{2,3} R. Vijayakumar,¹ N. V. Giridharan²

¹ PG and Research Department of Physics, Andavan Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli 620005

² Department of Physics, National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli 620015

³ Department of Physics, PSNA College of Engineering and Technology, Dindugal 624622

* Corresponding Author: shankar.vibration@gmail.com (9944340622)

Abstract

Pure and La doped bismuth titanate $\text{Bi}_{4-x}\text{La}_x\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ ($x=0, 0.15, 0.25, 0.5, 1$) polycrystals were prepared by sol-gel process. The crystalline behaviours of all prepared powders were studied by X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD), and the phases were confirmed with JCPDS data. As the La-concentration increases, the shifting of XRD peaks and also merging of certain peaks were observed related to a possible structure change from orthorhombic to tetragonal [1]. This suggested the high centre of symmetry for La doped sample. Differential thermal analysis has been employed to determine the glass transition temperature. DTA measurements were recorded in the temperature range 300° to 800° C, and the phase transition ferro- to para- electric transition has been observed [2]. The value of dielectric constant were decreased with increasing the frequency. Also Ferroelectric loops were obtained for the BT and BLT powders at room temperature. So, the dielectric constant decreases with increasing frequency as well as value of dielectric constant is increased by increasing La concentration [3]. From DTA analysis the Curie temperature is found to lower values by increasing La concentration. Also Hysteresis loops were obtained for both pure and La doped systems, but by La concentration increasing, the space charge polarization cannot keep up with change of electric field, so that the remnant polarization and coercive field decrease.

Keywords: Bismuth Titanates, Doping Effect, Structural Transition, ferro- to para- electric transition

References

- [1] A. Z. Simoes, B. D. Stojanovic, M. A. Ramirez, A. A. Cavalheiro, E. Longo, J. A. Varela, *Ceramics International*, 34 (2008) 257-261
- [2] Lin Xue, Guan Qing Feng, Li Hai Bo, Liu Yang and Zou Guang Tian, *Science China Physics, Mechanics and Astronomy*, 55 (2012) 33-39
- [3] 12.Nikolina Pavloc, Vladimir Koval, Jan Dusza, Vladimir, *Ceramics International*, 37 (2011) 487-492